

Influence of Motivation and Career Development on Employee Performance at Pt. Pixel Perdana Jaya

Nur Anisa Aniarti, Perbanas Institute

Abstract:- This research aims to find out the significance of the influence of Motivation, and Career Development on employee performance at PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya. The population in the study was 60 employees. Sampling technique uses the non probability sampling method with a type of saturated sampling. The data collection techniques used in this study are using interview techniques and with the dissemination of questionnaires. The analysis method used in this study is a linear regression model where in the processing of data using the Statistical Program for Social Science (SPSS) version 20 program. The results showed that motivation and career development have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Keywords:- Motivation, Career Development, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are the most important part of a company that has the potential to thrive and actively drive productivity in meeting company goals. Managing employees is not just a job description and regulations that must be adhered to, but there needs to be a synergistic relationship between the company and employees.

Therefore, the company must have and prepare and place reliable, ready and responsive human resources in accordance with the duties and responsibilities in the positions and positions that have been entrusted to the human resources in order to be able to contribute optimally in the efforts to achieve the company's goals.

One of the success factors of the company is supported by employee performance. In a work with regulation, operational and administrative to be a constructive part in controlling employees, but with motivational support, career development and guidance direction will support

supervision and achieve better performance often with current management and workforce developments.

With high work motivation employees will work hard to carry out their work, but if the motivation of work is low then instead make not eager work and easy to give up. Motivation is a series of encouragement to someone to take action to achieve the desired goal.

In addition to providing motivation, a very important factor in efforts to improve employee performance is the career development factor. Organizations are required to be able to adapt and move quickly with change. Changes in the organizational structure are made so that the organization can immediately act with various changes that have occurred. The impact on career development is to support the effectiveness of individuals and organizations in achieving goals. Career advancement is often an obsession of many working people and is often more of a concern for them than the company's leadership.

PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya in 2016 was appointed as the official distributor of Philips television in Indonesia. The company has also prepared two new variants of Philips TVs with different screen dimensions for the country market. Appointment of PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya as a distributor of Philips TVs in Indonesia was conducted by TP Vision, a Taiwanese subsidiary of TPV Technology which is the holder of the Philips TV brand worldwide, in August 2016.

One of the companies in the field of distributors Philips was first established in 2007, and in 2011 PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya was appointed as Philips distributor for Jakarta and Java. Some of the problems that occur in PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya is an employee's lack of awareness of absenteeism and a wide range of issues that include motivation and career development. The problem faced by the company is that there are still many employees who are absent late during working hours. This can be seen from the monthly attendance data of PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya.

Information	November- December, Sespakes office	November- December, warehouse office	January - February , Sespakes office	January - February , warehouse office
Late	113	165	117	174
Alpha	20	102	38	104
Jumlah	133	267	155	278

Table 1: Employee attendance data PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya

Source : Data from PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya, 2017-2018

Based on table 1 regarding attendance data at PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya looks at the total number of employees and the total attendance of employees. In November - February the number of employees who are late to attend and do not enter work has increased so that the level of employee discipline

decreases. This needs to get special attention from the HRD department to prevent the increasing level of discipline.

Previous research conducted by Audra Bianca et all in 2014, after syntax modifications, it was found that there was a positive and significant influence between motivation and

career development on job satisfaction with standard factor load values of 0.53 and 0.3 motivation and career development on employee performance with standard factor load values of 0.24 and 0.56 and job satisfaction on employee performance with standard factor load values of 0.31. And career development has a real partial effect on employee performance, meaning that independent variable consisting of work discipline, motivation, and career development, affect dependent variables that are employee performance..

- Research purposes
 - To analyze the influence of motivation on employee performance on PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya.
 - To analyze the influence of career development on employee performance on PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Performance

Wirawan (2009) defines performance as the output generated by the functions or indicators of a job or profession over a period of time.

Wirawan (2015: 53) the dimension of performance is the quality or face of a job or activity that occurs in the workplace that is conducive to measurement. The performance dimension provides a tool for describing the overall scope of activities at work. Meanwhile, responsibilities and obligations provide a description of depersonalization.

According to Wirawan (2015: 54), the dimensions of performance are grouped into three types, **achievements, work behaviors, and personal traits related to work.**

B. Motivation

According to Rivai Et al (2015: 607) motivation is part of attitudes and values that influence individuals to achieve specific things in accordance with individual goals.

According to Greenberg and Baron (in Wibowo, 2016) argues that motivation is a series of processes that arouse, direct, and maintain human behavior towards achieving goals.

According to Sedarmayanti (2017) motivation, is a willingness to issue a high level of effort towards the goals of the organization conditioned by the ability of that effort to meet individual needs.

C. Career Development

According to Veitzhal Rivai (2015: 212) career development is the process of increasing the workability of

individuals achieved in order to achieve the desired career.

Career development is an effort made by organizations in planning the careers of their employees, referred to as career management, including planning, implementing, and career advancement (Sinambela, 2017: 260).

III. METHODOLOGY

The research is being designed utilizing a human resource management approach, which includes operational variables, data collection methods and information gathering, population definition, sample size calculation, and sampling procedures. The preliminary research is followed by the formulation of construct variables in this study. The goal and purpose of this study are to characterize and show the interrelationships between the above-mentioned research variables. This study used a descriptive and verification approach, as well as a causal research design, to examine the relationship and influence of exogenous and endogenous variables.

The process of observation in this research is using time horizon with cross section/one shot, the collective data is obtained from the research done in 2018, the unit of analysis are the employee of the IT provider products and services company in Jakarta, Indonesia. The design of analysis is using Statistical Program for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.

The population in this study was 60 employees. The sampling technique uses the non probability sampling method with a type of saturated sampling. This is used when the population is relatively small. So the sample in this study is 60 people according to the number of population that has been determined.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

In this discussion, the author will describe the results of the questionnaire data that has been distributed to respondents using the help of the SPSS program version 20, with the following description:

- **Analysis of the Influence of Motivation on Employee Performance**

B. Determination Coefficient Analysis

Determination coefficient analysis is an analysis used to determine how much motivation contributes to employee performance.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.659 ^a	.434	.424	5.876

Table 2: Determination Coefficient Analysis

a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation

From the results of spss data processing version 20 as in the table above, the value of R Square is 0.434, the

coefficient of determination (KD) = $R^2 \times 100\%$ which is $0.434 \times 100\% = 43.4\%$. This means that the influence of

Motivation on Employee Performance by 43.4% and the remaining 56.6% is influenced by other variables such as Career Development, Job Satisfaction, Compensation etc..

Regression coefficient analysis is an analysis to analyze the influence between motivations on employee performance.

C. Regression Coefficient Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	16.639	3.377		4.928	.000
Motivasi	.619	.093	.659	6.665	.000

Table 3: Regression Coefficient Analysis

Coefficients^a

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

From the results of spss data processing version 20 as in the table above, the regression equation is $Y = 16.639 + 0.619 X1$, meaning that if motivation is eliminated (e.g. $X1 = 0$), then employee performance is only 16,639. As for motivation if improved, there will be changes in employee performance of 0.619.

t count is greater than t table or $6.665 > 1,672$ or H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that motivation has a significant positive influence on employee performance.

• Analysis of the Influence of Career Development on Employee Performance

D. Hypothesis Test T- test

From the results of data processing SPSS version 20 as the table above is known t calculate = 6,665. Using $\alpha = 5\%$ (n-k) is known the value of t table 5% ($60 - 2$) = 1,672. that

E. Determination Coefficient Analysis

Determination coefficient analysis is an analysis used to determine how much career development contributes to employee performance.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.753 ^a	.566	.559	5.142

Table 4: Determination Coefficient Analysis

a. Predictors: (Constant), employee performance

From the results of spss data processing version 20 as tabled above, the value of R Square is 0.566, then the coefficient of determination (KD) = $R^2 \times 100\%$ which is $0.566 \times 100\% = 56.6\%$. This means that the effect of Career Development on Employee Performance by 56.6% and the remaining 43.4% is influenced by other variables.

F. Regression Coefficient Analysis

Regression coefficient analysis is an analysis to analyze the influence between Career Development on Employee Performance.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	10.799	3.258		3.315	.002
Pengembangan Karier	.765	.088	.753	8.705	.000

Table 5: Regression Coefficient Analysis

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

From the results of spss data processing version 20 as tabled above, the regression equation is $Y = 10.799 + 0.765 X2$, meaning that if career development is eliminated (e.g. $X2 = 0$), then employee performance is only 10,799. As for Career Development if improved, there will be changes in Employee Performance by 0.765.

G. Hypothesis Test T- test

From the results of data processing SPSS version 20 in the table above is known t calculate = 8,705. Using $\alpha = 5\%$ (n-k) is known the value of t table 5% ($60 - 2$) = 1,672. that t count is greater than t table or $8.705 > 1,672$ or H_0 rejected and H_a accepted. This means that career development has a significant positive influence on employee performance.

• **Analysis of the Influence of Motivation and Career Development on Employee Performance**

H. Determination Coefficient Analysis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.812 ^a	.660	.648	4.592

Table 6: Determination Coefficient Analysis

a. Predictors: (Constant), Motivation, Career Development

From the results of spss data processing version 20 as tabled above, the value of R square is 0.660, the coefficient of determination (KD) = R² x 100% which is 0.660 x 100% = 66.0%. It can be concluded that the magnitude of the

influence of Motivation and Career Development together on Employee Performance by 66.0% and the remaining 34.0% is influenced by other variables.

I. Regression Coefficient Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.842	3.167		1.844	.070
1 Motivasi	.339	.086	.361	3.963	.000
Pengembangan Karier	.570	.093	.561	6.162	.000

Table 7: Regression Coefficient Analysis

Coefficients^a

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

From the results of spss data processing version 20 such as the regression equation table of $Y = 5.842 + 0.339 X1 + 0.570 X2$, meaning that if motivation and career development are eliminated (e.g. $X1, X2 = 0$), then employee performance is only 5,842. But if motivation increases then there will be a change in employee performance of 0.339 and if career development increases then there will be a change in employee performance of 0.57. Motivation and Career Development affect Employee Performance.

time in order to get promotion and the company should provide education and training in career development for employees in order to obtain a career development program.

RECOMMENDATION

- Employee Performance, To overcome these problems, the company should identify problems by developing an employee mindset about the rhythm of the work in the direction.
- The influence of motivation on employee performance, the company should improve job satisfaction and employee performance through employee work motivation, compensation and appropriate rewards are not priorities, because there are still other things that can be used as employee work motivation increases including the possibility of development and relationships with employees. In addition to providing opportunities to develop can also be by strengthening the relationship of fellow employees either in one work unit or outside the work unit. Regular meetings formally or informally can also bring relationships closer to employees..
- Career development influence on employee performance, career development has a significant influence on employee performance at PT. Pixel Perdana Jaya for that the company should pay attention to the position of employees who have worked in the company for a long

REFERENCE

- [1.] Arikunto, S. 2010. *Prosedurpenelitian :Suatu Pendekatan Praktik.* (EdisiRevisi). Jakarta : Rineka Cipta
- [2.] Bangun, Wilson. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia.* Edisikeenam. Jakarta :Erlangga.
- [3.] Eko, Suparno. (2015). *Manajemen Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia.* Yogyakarta : Pustaka Pelajar.
- [4.] Kadarisman. (2014). *Manajemen Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia.* Jakarta :Rajawali Pers.
- [5.] Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu AA. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan.* Bandung : PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- [6.] Rivai, Veitzhal dan Mansyur, Thoby Mutis, Willy Arafah. (2015). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusiauntuk Perusahaan.* Jakarta :Rajawali Pers.
- [7.] Robbins & Coutler. (2016). *Manajemen.* Edisi Ketigabelas. Jakarta :Erlangga.
- [8.] Sedarmayanti. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Reformasi Birokrasi dan ManajemenPegawai Negeri Sipil.* Edisi Revisi. Bandung : PT. RefikaAditama.
- [9.] Sinambela, Poltak. (2017). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia.* Jakarta : PT. Bumi Aksara.
- [10.] Sugiyono. (2008). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D.* Bandung: Alfabeta
- [11.] Sugiyono. (2013). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan*

Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D.
Bandung: Alfabeta

- [12.] Sutrisno, Edy. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Edisi Pertama. Jakarta :Prenadamedia Group.
- [13.] Suwatno. (2016). *Manajemen SDM dalam Organisasi Publik dan Bisnis*. Bandung :Alfabeta.
- [14.] Wibowo. (2016). *Manajemen Kinerja*. Edisi Kelima. Jakarta :Rajawali Pers.
- [15.] Wirawan. (2015). *Teori Aplikasi dan Penelitian :Evaluasi Kinerja SumberDayaManusia*. Jakarta :SalembaEmpat.
- [16.] Yusuf, Arif. (2016). *Pemahaman Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Yogyakarta : PT. BukuSeru.